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Ministry Dynamics in the 21st Century

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INTRODUCTION

The 21st Century is a computerized and digitalized age or an era with high level of advance technological innovations and inventions, where most activities, businesses, transactions, advertisements relationships and many more are being carried out online, known as the internet world. This is a period where people, most especially the younger ones are engrossed and glued to their handsets, tables, laptops or computers as the case may be, browsing from one site to another with rapt attention and keen interest searching or looking for the latest information and updates on issues and happenings around the world, as the world has become a Global Village where Information is gotten at the tip of the fingers. On the internet, they longed for pleasure, companionship entertainment, fun, and the likes.

The 21st century being the internet age is also categorize with the mix multitudes, the good, the bad and the ugly. It has people with cloned faces with cloned hearts, pretending to be what there are not. This era, is characterized with pretentious, deceptive and fraudulent individuals with different activities, such that if care is not taken, even the very elects of the Lord will be deceived or misled. The 21st century is a period where iniquity shall abound as predicted by Jesus Christ. Matt 24:12, "And because iniquity shall abound, the Love of many shall wax cold" 1Tim 3:1-5, further said, this know also, that in the last days, perilous times shall come. For men shall be lovers of their own selves, covetous, boasters, proud, blasphemers, disobedient to parents, unthankful, unholy, without natural affection, truce breakers, false accusers,, incontinent, fierce, dispensers of those that are good. Having a form of godliness but denying the power thereof, from such, turn away". This is the situation of the 21st century, with different religious activists, religious fanatics or extremist, the idealists, and philosophers. Most of these religionists are devoted to different kinds of gods and deities with different kinds of diabolic and fetish practices, doctrines and beliefs, attempting to impress their victims with fake promises. The good thing is that, more people can be reached at a time.

Building a Great Ministry in the 21st century is a huge task and very demanding due to the complex nature of our modern society. It takes the grace of God and with the help of the Holy Spirit to build a great, notable and remarkable ministry. To also build a successful ministry in this 21st century, strategic steps have to be deployed such as branding and packaging with high level of expertise, professionalism, and rightful application of all the available resources at one's disposal that will be appealing, motivating inspiring and attractive to behold. As it's said that the way you dress will be the way you will be addressed. What you have to offer and how you present it will determine who will want to identify with you. Ministry is not entertainment nor a money making venture, but inspiring and hope giving, encouraging and comforting. Ministry is to Heal the Sick,

and to Bind the broken hearted. Deliverance to the Oppressed, Light to them that are in Darkness, Freedom and Liberty to them that are bound. To build a great ministry is to provide comfort, direct and redirect people's feelings though, actions and steps towards the right direction. Building A Great Ministry is building individuals, investing in their spirit, soul and body, bringing them to the knowledge of God, to be conformed to the image of Jesus Christ. Building A Great Ministry is not building cathedrals, auditoriums, skyscrapers mansions. Building A Great Ministry is building, shaping, patterning their lives after God's will and purpose, bringing God's will to bear in the minds of the people.

Talking about Building a Great Ministry; what then is ministry?

- (1) First of all, ministry is a call to service unto God and unto humanity. Act 13:1-2
- (2) Ministry is an assignment given to individuals to edify the body of Christ which is the church.
- (3) Ministry is a gift, distributed to individuals by the Holy Spirit, and it's by the grace of God, not by merit, and according to their several abilities. Matt 25:15 Eph 4:8-10, 1Cor 12:4-11
- (4) Ministry is an activity, carried out by gifted individuals that serves God's purpose and meets the needs of the people. Act 6:1-3.

Types of Ministries

There are different types of ministries given to different people for specific purposes. One thing is common with the collective aspects of the ministries, which is, fulfilling God agenda, as they are gifts from God.

- (1) The fivefold ministry, which comprises, the Apostles, the Prophets, the Pastors, the Evangelists and the Teachers are involve in missionary activities around the world. They are into church planting, outreaches and evangelism, discipleship training, teaching, counseling, and catering for the flocks of God. These set run with the GO -YE Command to ensure that the gospel is spread across the world and the flocks are cared for. Matt 28:18-20, Mk 16:15-26, Eph 4:9-11
- (2) Prayer/Intercessory Ministry: These are set of people God have placed as watchmen over cities, churches and individuals. These are intercessors, and prayer warriors making intercession for the work of the ministry, for the saints, and those in power and authority. Eoh 6:18, 2Tim 3:1, 1Tim 2:2-3, 2 Cor 1:11, Ps 122:6.
- (3) Music/Singing Ministry: To inspire congregational worship and fellowship, enhance spiritual growth, edify the saints, honor and adore God. Ps 111:1, Col 3:16, Ps 98:1-7.

(4) Women ministry: Titus 2:3-5, talks about women ministry thus, "The aged women likewise that they be a behavior as become the holiness, not false accusers, not given to much wine, teachers of good things, that they may teach the younger women to be sober, to love their husbands, and to love their children. To be discreet, chaste, keepers of home, good, obedient to their own husband's, that the word of God be not blasphemed" The ministry of teaching, Impartation and custodians of knowledge, moral, values, on the younger ones.

(5) Teaching Ministry: These categories of teachers may not necessarily function within the fivefold ministry but are gifted to teach Sunday School Classes, bible study, at homes, home cell centers, and Christian Colleges and Theological seminaries. Rom 12:6-7.

(6) Financial/Giving Ministry: God blesses these ministers to sponsor Missions and Outreaches, assist the needy and the less privileged. Rom12:6-8

(7) Hospitality/Visiting Ministry: Identifying with the sick, depressed those in prison and the likes. Matt 25:34-36 Rom12:10

(8) Counseling Ministry: This is the ministry that render counseling services to those undergoing emotional trauma, crises in marriages, or about to get married. They settle disputes and reconcile relationships. 2Cor 5:18.

(9) Youth Ministry; Youth Ministry encompasses a variety of ministerial programming and outreach activities that are targeted at the youth to make them realize themselves on time and guide them through the right channel.

(10) Children Ministry: Children Ministry also help in preparing the children for the future.

(11) Widow Ministry: This ministry caters mainly for the widows through counseling, Entrepreneurship, financial empowerment and support.

(12) Deliverance and Healing Ministry: To some are given the ministry of deliverance and Healing. They could be among the fivefold ministry or not. 1 Cir 12:4-11.

Purpose of Ministry

(1) To build and establish good relationship and fellowship between God and man

(2) To spread the gospel of our Lord Jesus Christ across the world, showcasing the love, care and redemption work for man

(3); The purpose of ministry is to provide pastoral care, nurture spiritual growth within the congregation and ultimately help Christians develop a deeper relationship with God, by facilitating worship, discipleship, evangelism and community service.

(4) According to the book of Eph 4:12-13, it says that the gifts and talents given to men is for the perfecting of the saints, for the work of the ministry, for the edifying of the body of Christ till we all come to the unity of the faith, and of the knowledge of the son of God, unto a perfect man, unto the measure of the stature of the fullness of Christ. Ministry must fulfill all these aspects, if not, then it's not ministry.

HOW TO BUILD A GREAT MINISTRY

1 Cor 3:9, ' For we are laborers together with God, ye are God's husbandry, ye are God's building'

Building A Great Ministry can never be achieved alone but with God as God is doing his work through us as vessels.

(1) Have a clear vision: Since ministry is a vision, a gift or an assignment from God , it's expected that the vision carrier understands the vision clear, and make it plain, without ambiguity so that those who will come along will also run with the vision according to specifications. Hab 2:2

(2) Every vision is for an appointed time. There's a set time for every assignment to kick off. If you want to build a great ministry, don't rush into ministry, don't compare yourself with others, ministry is never a competition. Hab 2:3

(3) For one to build a great ministry, know that ministry is an assignment, a calling, a responsibility given to individuals on trust. It's not all about how you feel it should be done, but how the master want it done. Be careful how you build.

(4) Build with the mindset that ministry is rendering services unto God on behalf of man. To please and glorify God. Don't ever build ministry base on personal ideas or on assumptions.

(5) Building ministry is taking one systematic step to another. Don't ever doubt yourself, be confident, bold and courageous. Don't be moved by challenges and trails, oppositions and difficulties. Remain focus and resolute. Don't depend on your flesh but on the Holy Spirit. 1Tim 2:1-3

(6) As a great ministry builder, have mentors spiritual father's, and leaders you will go to once a while for counseling and advise. Those that will tell you the truth when you are wrong or go astray. Mentors that will rebuke and call you back to order when you err. 2Tim 2:1-7

(7) 1cor 3:10, Talks about team work and collective responsibility. 'According to the grace of God, which is given unto me, as a wise master builder, I have laid the foundation, and another build the thereon. But let ever man take heed how he build the thereupon" To build a great ministry, it takes a great team. Build a strong and formidable team that will help build a great ministry, and take caution how to build.

(8) Networking: Networking with like-minded colleagues, core workers and reputable organizations is another formidable way of building a great ministry. Sharing ideas, facilities, exchange of pulpits adds flavor to ministry. 1Cor 3:10

(9) Regular training and education must never be over looked while building a great ministry. Study to show yourself approved. 2Tim 2:15

(10) Prayer and Fasting is another area that helps in building a great ministry. This is where to get inspiration, revelations and empowerment for the work of the ministry. As there are some stubborn situations that can only be handled by prayer and fasting.

(11) 1 Cor 3:14, ' If any man's s work abide which he hath built thereupon, he shall receive a reward'

Do the work of the ministry to please God, rather than men. It's God who gave the assignment, and he's the one to assess and reward.

(12) God resist the proud but gives grace to the humble. Be humble and enjoy in God's grace to build a great ministry. Jam 4:6, 1Pet 5:6-7

MINISTRY DYNAMICS THAT THRIVE IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Dynamics is a process or system characterized by constant change, activity or progress. It's a positive way, attitude method or mechanism that is initiated that propels, stimulates or effects progress, even in the midst of challenges, trails, difficulties or oppositions. Ministry Dynamics is the interaction and relationships among the ministry team force, as ministry cannot thrive in isolation. No man, they say, is an island. Dynamics has to do with laudable ideas, systematic, strategic steps employed in order to meet a desired objectives. A measure to be taken to produce effective change that influence progress.

As there are different gifts, talents, potentials endowed in individuals by the Holy Spirit, there must be a harmonization, coordination, blending, planning for a ministry to thrive. Of all the ministerial

gifts mentioned earlier, the prayer, singing, teaching giving, prophecy, and the rest of them must be properly harnessed for programs to measure up to the demands and expectations of ministry, which primarily is to glorify God and meet the needs of the people.

Thrive

To thrive on the other hand is to grow, succeed, and flourish. To progress towards, or realize a great goal, despite unpleasant circumstances.

The 21st century being characterized by advance technological innovations where almost everyone is online, seeking or doing one thing or the other, ministry dynamics that thrives in the 21st century is the rightful application of all ministry components, to meet the needs of the targeted audience on the internet. A ministry can be able to reach out to thousands and millions of people online at the same time all over the world, if properly organized. Note that for the fact that 21st activities are focused online, does not necessarily mean that ministry should concentrate mainly on the internet, as activities are both online and onsite. On-site programs such as church services, crusades, seminars, conferences pray rallies and retreats, must be well organized to attract people to God, even as their needs are being met

CONCLUSION

Ministry is not in titles but in service, and ministry can only be fulfilled if the services are geared towards glorifying God and meeting man's needs. The moment service is removed from ministry, then it's no longer ministry but business, or a mere show or jamboree. Building A Great Ministry requires diligence, endurance, doggedness, discipline, commitment and dedication to service.

In building a great ministry, one must depend solemnly on God through the power and influence of the Holy Spirit, adhering to every instructions as they come. Obedience and humility will also qualify one to enjoy grace for service. Ministry dynamics is the combination and harmonization of all components and integral parts of individual gifts, talents, skills, potentials, resources to effect or actualize meaningful and fulfill service unto God and humanity, as no part is to be considered insignificant to be over looked or ignored.

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